

MNEMOSINE DIGITAL LIBRARY. TOWARDS A COOPERATIVE AND INTERDISCIPLINARY KNOWLEDGE BASE

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Summary

The impulse in recent decades of the so-called cultural and post-colonial studies and the massive digitisation of bibliographic repertoires open up new perspectives for the study of the literature of the Silver Age in the Hispanic world. To this end, the *Mnemosine* Digital Library offers the researcher a collaborative environment in which to explore new approaches, through the articulation of workflows that interact on a model of linked data. This article describes the conformation of this platform as an interdisciplinary open science laboratory and the challenges to ensure the sustainability of its projection as a Smart Library.

The *Mnemosine* Digital Library: innovation and interdisciplinarity

The development of the Digital Humanities has favoured the existence of an ecosystem of tools and documentary repositories available to the academic community, nourished by ambitious projects of massive digitization of contents in institutions of different nature and scope. This process, initiated in the last decade of the 20th century, offers a wide and heterogeneous range of sources, accessible to the researcher in a ubiquitous and asynchronous way, favouring not only a re-reading of traditional theoretical frameworks, but also a genuine methodological renewal.

In this sense, it is worth recalling the development of currents such as the so-called "digital history"¹ whose postulates are linked to the rise of a "public history", complementary phenomena inspired by the desire to democratise access to

¹ Understanding this concept from a global perspective in which the historian's archive moves from a static and specialised space to a nomadic space with immaterial content such as the web, defined not only by the sources it uses - digital sources - but also "by the relationship itself with computer technology, with databases, hypertextualisation and networks to create and share historical knowledge". (MELO FLÓREZ, Jairo Antonio, "Historia digital. La memoria en el archivo infinito." *Historia Crítica*, 43 (2011). 82-103.

<https://revistas.uniandes.edu.co/index.php/hiscrit/article/view/4230/3473>

knowledge thanks to technologies that allow new voices to be heard and integrated into research, reaching a wider public in the transfer of information.

In this sense, the *Mnemosine Digital Library*² embodies a pioneering initiative in its field. Unlike most academic portals specialising in the Humanities, *Mnemosine* is not just a native digital library with archiving, cataloguing and bibliographic search capabilities. Its technological platform articulates the research activity of the LOEP Group³, created in 2007, committed to the rescue and revaluation of an alternative canon represented by "rare and forgotten" texts, exponents of an ignored or neglected literature encompassed within the so-called "Other Silver Age". With this approach, *Mnemosine* is the backbone of a methodology that focuses on the logic of the semantic web, articulated on linked data that are captured in institutional repositories of recognised reliability and enriched, within the dynamics of the research team's own work, to be offered later, in open access, to the academic community and the public.

The need underlying this technological resolution has a long history, arising long before *Mnemosine* began to be developed. Authors such as José-Carlos Mainer, Ángela Ena Bordonada or Dolores Romero, among many others, together with currents such as the so-called Gender Studies, questioned the very concept of the literary canon in the Silver Age at the beginning of the 21st century, conceiving it as a dynamic entity of a cultural nature, permeable to the social and historical reality of each moment and, therefore, not constrained within the framework of conventional literary genres, specific generations, nor limited to the work of a closed cast of renowned figures. As a consequence, research work and scientific meetings were held that advocated an integrating perspective, in which texts that had hitherto been undervalued took on a leading role as the object of research. As Dolores Romero has pointed out, this methodological change cannot be understood without the help of a new digital history, in which advances in technology allow radical changes in research methods, with an ontological dimension - due to the broadening of the object of study, thanks to access to a greater number of works - but also an epistemological one (with new approaches and categories of analysis, unattainable in analogue environments).

Therefore, the aim was not only to rescue and enhance the value of a hitherto forgotten bibliographic heritage, but also to promote literary studies from a cultural and necessarily transdisciplinary approach, which transcends the text to explore its underlying discourse and the mentality of the reading public. This made it necessary to integrate into the research elements related to the historical, social, biographical and cultural context of the work and its author, in order to identify literary

² <http://repositorios.fdi.ucm.es/mnemosine/>

³ <https://www.ucm.es/loep>

cartographies and networks of relationships; an objective that could not be satisfied by the information available until then in conventional bibliographic catalogues, which were more focused on the external, literal or superficial description of format and content.⁴

For all these reasons, the boom in technologies associated with the Web 2.0 ecosystem led to the creation of the collaborative environments required by this new way of working. Among its requirements were the interactivity and interoperability of repositories and solutions, and the articulation of a linked data model. And as raw material, it was necessary to enable a representative web of metadata and texts, which would not have been feasible to collect by traditional mechanisms of selection and cataloguing of bibliographic resources.

The combination of this theoretical background, which called for the need for a new approach, with the benefits of new technologies were the ingredients that made it possible to commit since 2010 to a basic infrastructure that would allow the development of innovative lines of work, unfeasible until then. The idea materialised in 2012 with the granting of funding by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through the R&D project *Electronic Desks for Literatures-2* (Ref. FFI2012-34666). This is the milestone that marks the first steps in the development of the *Mnemosine* platform, combining the efforts of LOEP and the research group of the Faculty of Computer Science ILSA (Implementation of Language-Driven Software and Applications) to address both the construction of the hardware and software infrastructure, as well as the first tasks of selection and data collection, prior to the opening of the service in 2015.⁵

The technological solution, conceived with an interdisciplinary approach from the outset, combined the contribution of experts in disciplines such as philology and computer science with content curation techniques from the field of librarianship, which were essential to guarantee the quality of the data. The activity subsequently developed on *Mnemosine* only consolidated this interdisciplinary vocation, with the design of collections that configured the platform's architecture and data model.

⁴ ROMERO LÓPEZ, Dolores. "Archivos, repositorios y bibliotecas digitales: hacia una Historia Digital de la Edad de Plata. *Signa. Revista de la Asociación Española de Semiótica*, 30 (2021):17-30. <https://doi.org/10.5944/signa.vol30.2021.29296>.

⁵ A detailed description of the beginnings of the platform can be found in: GONZÁLEZ SORIANO, José Miguel. "*Mnemosine*: Biblioteca digital de la otra Edad de Plata (orígenes, contenidos, perspectivas)", *Signa. Revista de la Asociación Española de Semiótica*, 30 (2021):36-40. <https://doi.org/10.5944/signa.vol30.2021.29297>

Successive projects, always in collaboration with the ILSA group of the Faculty of Computer Science, incorporated new functionality and content⁶. Among them, the collaboration with the National Library of Spain to enrich some of the texts referenced in *Mnemosine*, with the aim of creating interactive editions for teaching purposes, stands out. The *eLITE-CM* project, *Electronic literary edition* (H2015/HUM-3426) also aimed to strengthen the Digital Library's vocation as an innovation laboratory, favouring the creation of prototypes and pilots whose experience could be extrapolated to other contexts. The result of this initiative was the creation of the collection christened "La Edad de Plata Interactiva", in the context of the agreement with Red.es, which allowed the publication of works in three initial thematic lines: "La Mujer Moderna en la Edad de Plata", "Literatura infantil" and "Madrid en la Edad de Plata", which we will discuss later.⁷

Collaborative platform and data reuse

The functional and technical requirements, described above, sought to define the architecture of a system that would feed the "infinite archive" of which William J. Turkel spoke ("Methodology for the Infinite Archive") in the context of a new digital history. This aspiration requires a fabric of delocalised and interconnected data that can be interrogated from different approaches by researchers:

Humanists won't be able to think of themselves as makers until we create spaces for them to make things in.⁸

Mnemosine has designed a collaborative platform, conceived more as a tool than a repository, as opposed to the static data model of a conventional library. Its aim is to enable a laboratory of innovation, oriented towards the generation of new knowledge, and not only focused on the preservation of the bibliographic legacy.

Thus, the architecture of this solution is inspired by the postulates of an open and reusable science, incorporating the necessary functionality to automatically capture data related to texts and authors, relegated to oblivion by the official canon for their subsequent analysis and re-reading. In this process, the metadata schema

⁶ The development of the *Mnemosine* Digital Library has been funded mainly by the Plan Estatal de I+D+i (Ref. FF12012-34666 and Ref. RTI2018-095522-B-I00) and the Consejería de Educación, Juventud y Deporte de la Comunidad de Madrid (H215/HUm-34-26).

⁷ <https://www.ucm.es/edicionliterariaelectronica> See also ROMERO LÓPEZ, Dolores. "Mnemosine, la biblioteca digital académica como canon alternativo para el estudio de la Edad de Plata (1868-1936)". MORALES SÁNCHEZ, María Isabel, COSTA, Paulo and BALÇA, Ángela (ed. lit.). *Literatura y prácticas digitales: una mirada interdisciplinar alrededor de la formación literaria* (Valencia: Tirant Lo Blanch, 2024).

⁸ TURKLE. W. J. (2005-2008). *Digital History Hacks. Methodology for the Infinite Archive*. At <http://digitalhistoryhacks.blogspot.com.es>

constitutes the raw material of the research work, seeking to identify relationships between different categories of analysis, which are reconsidered from different angles. The name chosen for the tool, in fact, is a declaration of intent, since in classical mythology Mnemosine is the personification of memory and the mother of all muses, symbolising the importance of preserving the inherited cultural legacy as an inspiration for generating new knowledge, within a circular working dynamic that feeds back on itself.

Figure 1. Functional architecture of Mnemosine as an open science lab (source: own elaboration)

The construction of the platform and its subsequent development has gone through different phases. The first, within this iterative process, addressed the need to locate texts and authors in repositories where the quality of the data was guaranteed, as is the case of *HathiTrust Digital Library*, through the *Biblioteca Complutense* and the *Biblioteca Digital Hispánica*, later incorporating documentary funds from other institutions such as the *Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut* (IAI) in Berlin or the *Library of the University of California* at Los Angeles (UCLA Library).

The automatic loading operations in this tool are supported by capture and export *plugins*, implemented in the *Clavy* tool, an RIA (Rich Internet Application) developed by the ILSA research group (Software Language and Applications Engineering) of the

Complutense University, for the integrated management of digital collections. This management provides a catalogue of functionalities that include loading, cataloguing and custody operations, as well as data editing, enrichment and visualisation capabilities. *Clavy* is the cornerstone of the architecture of this solution, providing ETL (Extract, Transform and Load) features and allowing the integration of text annotation tools such as *@note*, geolocation (*Google Maps*) and editing (*Madgazine*). In addition, *Clavy* allows customisation of both the required functionality and the presentation layer in different digital libraries, *Mnemosine* being one of its instances.⁹

Figure 2. *Functionality of Mnemosine and Clavy.*
(source: own elaboration)

This technological solution allows interoperability with other systems through the use of semantic web standards such as RDF (Resource Description Framework), facilitating data import and export operations also through the use of standardised hypertext formats such as MARC21, XLS, XML or JSON. This aspect is basic for the design of a data model flexible enough to guarantee not only the interaction with

⁹ *Mnemosine* and *Clavy*: applications for the development of specific libraries for teaching and research. Office for the Transfer of Research Results (OTRI)
<https://www.ucm.es/otri/complutransfer-mnemosine-y-clavy-aplicaciones-para-la-gestion-de-bibliotecas-especificas-para-la-docencia-y-la-investigacion>

other systems, but also the recreation of cataloguing schemes in new collections and the enrichment of the collected data.

On the other hand, within the *Mnemosine* work model, the content curation phase is critical to guarantee the control of authorities and the accuracy and rigour of the data, avoiding duplications and establishing the interrelationships required by the object of study in each research, a task that is facilitated by the use of controlled vocabularies. *Clavy* allows new collections to be incorporated into *Mnemosine* in response to research needs, making it possible to search and interrelate the data in the repository. This requires, as will be seen below, enriching the classic cataloguing scheme (author, work, date of publication, etc.) with new attributes such as geographical coordinates, authors' addresses, professional activity, related associations or generic gender, which are rarely referenced in conventional bibliographic catalogues, but which are essential to address the cultural studies that are the objective of a tool such as *Mnemosine*.¹⁰

The creation of new collections on the platform is not decoupled from the research work; on the contrary, interaction with *Mnemosine* is an essential part of it. It makes it possible to identify patterns and trends, compare data and ultimately ratify or discard the initial hypotheses, through the processing of representative samples of information, interrogated with complex filters. In this sense, *Clavy*'s design provides very innovative elements that give greater power to the query engine, with the implementation of searches and faceted thesauri, directly related to the tool's capacity to manage digital collections through the reconfiguration of cataloguing schemes that are enriched with new attributes in the database.¹¹

Related to the previous point, it is worth noting, as indicated above, the constant interaction with *Mnemosine* within the workflow of the research itself, through the creation of new collections or repertoires, which will be described in detail below. In this way, apart from massive automatic capture processes, the use of the platform by researchers is materialised with the creation of specific collections, which are based on a prior selection of data, embodied in load files whose structure is adjusted to the grammar and syntax of the system. This operation allows the creation of new collections, the updating of which is coordinated by the researcher himself.

¹⁰ GONZÁLEZ SORIANO, José Miguel and GAYOSO CABADA, Joaquín. "*Mnemosine*: A Digital Platform for Research and Rediscovery of the Other Silver Age Spain". ROMERO LÓPEZ, Dolores and ZAMOSTNY, Jeffrey (eds.). *Towards the Digital Cultural History of the Other Silver Age Spain* (Bern: Peter Lang, 2022):89-93.

¹¹ The use of faceted search and schema reconfiguration is extensively explained in the doctoral thesis of Joaquín Gayoso, responsible for *Clavy*'s instance in *Mnemosine*. GAYOSO CABADA, Joaquín. "Digital collection management with reconfigurable cataloguing schemas" (PhD thesis, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 2017). <https://eprints.ucm.es/id/eprint/49761/>.

Figure 3. Architecture of the Mnemosine Digital Library (source: own elaboration)

Within this framework, the research results are made available to the academic community by publishing the *datasets* in repositories such as *Zenodo* or *GitHub*, to facilitate their reuse in other contexts. In addition, *Mnemosine's* commitment to an

open science model, which democratises access to information, is crowned by the activity of this digital library as a provider of *Wikidata* (Q98690245).¹²

Data model for the study of an alternative literary canon¹³

A key element in the architecture of the system is the relational search functionality on a linked data model, allowing cross-referencing information between different categories of analysis. As already indicated, the management of virtual objects and their internal relations is based on standardised languages such as RDF (*Resource Description Framework*) and schemas such as XML, which allow elements (classes) and their virtual relations (properties) to be defined on the basis of controlled vocabularies that facilitate interoperability in input and output flows with other systems. This aspect is key to allow the creation of ontologies specific to *Mnemosine*, but at the same time understandable by the data model of other repositories, in order to promote the reuse of datasets:

Some preexisting vocabularies that are useful for the definition of the *Mnemosine* ontology are Web Ontology Language (OWL), Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR), Friend of a Friend (FOAF) and Dublin Core. In addition to saving time, using pre-existing vocabularies makes it easier to recycle information from the *Mnemosine* database.¹⁴

The data model is developed from two main classes, "authors" and "works", which define cataloguing schemes with relevant attributes for each of them. In this way, for example, the digital object "person" establishes relations (properties) with other elements (the digital object "work") through terms (concepts) such as "author of", "translator of", etc. The development of *Mnemosine* has been incorporating collections that have required the identification of new classes, such as literary genres, sub-genres or macro-genres, based on the internal relationships between the main classes.

These connections and the incorporation of specific properties in the new collections by researchers have enriched their content, making it possible to identify networks that open up new horizons for research into the literary paradigm of the Silver Age. It is necessary to take into account the breadth of the period analysed, which extends from 1868 to 1936, and the need to catalogue the texts by

¹² *Mnemosine* instances on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/6629267> GitHub: <https://github.com/Biblioteca-Digital-Mnemosine/Data-Set> Wikidata: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q98690245>

¹³ For further details see ZAMOSTNY, Jeffrey (eds.). *Towards the Digital Cultural History of the Other Silver Age Spain* (Bern: Peter Lang, 2022):89-106.

¹⁴ ROMERO LÓPEZ, D., BUEREN GÓMEZ-ACEBO, J. L. and GAYOSO CABADA, J. (2017). "Modelling Kiosk Literary Collections for the Mnemosyne Digital Library." In *Kiosk Literature of Silver Age Spain: Modernity and Mass Culture*, J. Zamostny and S. Larson (eds.), 406. Bristol, UK / Chicago: Intellect.

identifying common patterns, but also singularities, in order to understand the evolution of cultural manifestations understood in a broad sense, under the coordinates of space and time. In addition, the description of aspects related to the intrahistory of the texts (translations, contact networks, etc.) and their interdisciplinary analysis in order to connect them with other artistic expressions and/or social phenomena are particularly important.

All this translates into the enrichment of the model with new metadata and the incorporation of different types of resources, such as access to the text of digitised works in open access or to their interactive editions, incorporating the link to the repository that holds them in the bibliographic records.

Mnemosine's vocation as a research platform is not only reflected in the internal logic for the creation of new collections. It is also evident in the consultation interface and in the languages used to navigate the system, which offer the user different entry points to the same content. Thus, access to the collections is based on three possible approaches that offer, respectively, a global, graphic and interactive vision of *Mnemosine's* documentary collection ("Digital Cartography"), the traditional classification of the history of literature ("History and Philology"), and the more heterogeneous vision of cultural studies, whose collections are accessed under the heading "Cultural Constellations".

The "Digital Cartography" represents an innovative formula for browsing through the different collections, especially oriented towards didactic purposes, which is why the graphic aspect has been enhanced, as well as interactivity. Based on the famous poster "Universo de la literatura española contemporánea" that Ernesto Giménez Caballero published in *La Gaceta Literaria* on 15 July 1927, the recreation of the map, implemented in the system, has a significant potential for its use in the classroom, by illustrating in a visual way the evolution of the classical approach of the history of literature to the field of cultural studies, which is much more plural, complex and transdisciplinary.¹⁵

On the other hand, access through the "History and Philology" section shows the user the traditional classification of content into works, authors and themes, focusing on the historical evolution of literary fact. The repository offers biographical data on 256 women and 1,477 writers, as well as access to 1,416 digitised monographs and 16 periodicals. On the classes (elements) of authors and works, collections are also offered according to literary genres, themes or aspects of the

¹⁵ A detailed explanation of the teaching use of this tool can be found at ROMERO LÓPEZ, Dolores. "*Mnemosine*, the academic digital library as an alternative canon for the study of the Silver Age (1868-1936)". MORALES SÁNCHEZ, María Isabel, COSTA, Paulo and BALÇA, Ángela (ed. lit.). *Literatura y prácticas digitales: una mirada interdisciplinar alrededor de la formación literaria* (Valencia: Tirant Lo Blanch, 2024).

writers' biographies, such as their sex or place of birth. In this way, it is possible to access a specific collection on women poets or writers born in Madrid, who represent a subset of the previous classes. Also, through this access point, it is possible to consult the collection "La Edad de Plata Interactiva" mentioned above, which, together with "Cartografía Digital", is probably the part of the documentary collection most specifically oriented towards dissemination and teaching activity.

However, *Mnemosine's* potential as a platform for collaborative and interdisciplinary research becomes even more evident in the "Cultural Constellations" section, which brings together different collections created by researchers. It is here that the digital object management engine allows an alternative canon to be analysed and configured from approaches that are not strictly literary. It also offers a space for experimentation in the data presentation layer, incorporating, for example, geolocalised information that allows the results of the research to be transferred through graphic supports, as in the case of plans or maps developed on Google Maps.

The following diagram shows the variety of topics covered by the different collections, classified according to the different interests of each research project:

Figure 4. *Cultural Constellations - Mnemosine* (source: own elaboration)

Nevertheless, these collections allow for cross-readings from different theoretical frameworks. Thus, for example, a quarter of these datasets analyse aspects related to gender and identity issues, giving visibility to texts and authors in many cases

unknown to the general public¹⁶. This is the case of the collection dedicated to lesbian literature, coordinated by Ángela Ena Bordonada and Patricia Barrera Velasco, which was a pioneer in its time within this line of research.

Another particularly interesting collection, in terms of the nature of this tool as a laboratory of innovation, is the one dedicated to Kiosk Literature, coordinated by Jeffrey Zamostny (Kansas State University), based on the existing holdings of the Ricardo Donoso-Cortés and Mesonero Romanos collection, held by the University of UCLA.¹⁷ In this case, the analysis hinges on the concept of "collection", which links data on works, authors and editions. The complexity of this work lies in exploring not only the production, but also the reading public and distribution channels and, for this reason, it lends itself to the testing of techniques such as data mining, applied to a large corpus of texts and metadata, enriched with information such as price, points of sale, periodicity, etc.¹⁸

The same is true of the collection dedicated to "Authors in Exile", directed by Lucía Cotarelo (GEXEL) in the framework of the research she undertook for her doctoral thesis. The cataloguing scheme associated with the "Person" class was enriched with metadata relevant to the object of study, such as the associations with which the author was linked, countries of destination, date of return to Spain, death in exile, friendships or languages in which he or she wrote, to cite a few examples. The collection also has geo-referenced information that makes it possible to trace the itineraries of exile and to delimit its scenarios, by destination and literary genre, as this researcher did to analyse the production of exiled poets on the East Coast of the United States. This modelling is very significant for tracing the landscapes of exile, choosing a literary genre particularly prone to the exploration of personal experiences and cultural transfers, as well as a host destination in which the rise of Hispanism projected a particular attraction for the reception of a highly qualified

¹⁶ In this case, moreover, *Mnemosine* provides very useful information for the development of projects outside the LOEP Research Group's activity, as is the case of the R+D+i project *Cartografías vitales. Biografías de autoras y editoras iberoamericanas. Primera escala* funded by the Ministry of Science and Innovation (PID2020-117997GB-100), whose PI is Professor Pura Fernández (Centro de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales, CSIC).

¹⁷ See ZAMOSTNY, Jeffrey, "La colección Ricardo Donoso-Cortés y Mesonero Romanos de literatura de kiosco, 1900-1967 (UCLA): presentación y catálogo", *Mediodía. Revista Hispánica de Rescate*, 1 (2018): 148-166.

¹⁸ ROMERO LÓPEZ, Dolores. "Mnemosine, la biblioteca digital académica como canon alternativo para el estudio de la Edad de Plata (1868-1936)". Véase también. ROMERO LÓPEZ, Dolores y BUEREN GÓMEZ-ACEVO, José Luis. "La colección Literatura de Quiosco en *Mnemosine*, Biblioteca Digital de la Otra Edad de Plata (1868-1936): hacia la redefinición del canon literario a través de metadatos". *Literatura: Teoría, Historia, Crítica*, vol. 21, núm. 1 (2019): 61-91.

exile profile, which enriched artistic and scientific activity in universities and research centres.¹⁹

These are just some of the examples of research work supported by *Mnemosine* as a research platform and laboratory for methodological experimentation, beyond a mere instrumental use subsidiary to technology, as occurs in other types of portals, used by the researcher as a mere documentary repository.

Finally, *Mnemosine* completes its functionality with the "Visualisations" section, which offers a graphic interface to transfer the results of data mining operations on the content of the different collections. As an example, the following case, where the dates of death of the writers of the Silver Age are analysed, demonstrates the impact of the Civil War as a cutting element that truncates the cultural trajectory developed up to that time:

Figure 5. *Mnemosine*/Visualisations²⁰

Collection management workflows

As we have seen, the way *Mnemosine* works is based on direct interaction with the research process. It is a circular working model that feeds back internally and can be reused in external systems. Since its launch (in beta) in 2015, the platform has implemented the workflow concept in its own definition and architecture,

¹⁹ COTARELO ESTEBAN, Lucía. "La colección "poetas en exilio en *Mnemosine*: Biblioteca digital de la otra edad de plata". ROMERO LÓPEZ, Dolores and SALAMANCA LÓPEZ, Manuel Joaquín (coords.). *Entornos digitales: Humanidades y ciencias sociales en la Universidad Complutense de Madrid*. Mexico: Red de Humanidades Digitales, 2018, pp. 25-41.

²⁰ <http://repositorios.fdi.ucm.es/mnemosine/stadisticasTest.php>

articulating an operational model based on the definition of tasks and responsibilities. This practice, commonly used in the definition of processes in any field, makes it possible to identify elements for improvement and risks to be mitigated, forming part of the quality model in any organisation.

Taking the above into account, the graphical representation of workflows is a good practice frequently applied in the field of software engineering, especially in the functional design phases, when defining what capacity a system requires, for what purpose and how it is to be implemented and who its users will be. Applying this philosophy to the field of Digital Humanities is particularly useful when it comes to ensuring the quality of data, the raw material for research in any of its disciplines, making it possible to identify paths for improvement in optimising the processes of importing, cleaning, cataloguing and transforming data.

All these phases are contemplated within the operations supported by *Mnemosine*, articulating the activity of different roles with well-defined responsibilities and capabilities in the interaction with the system. These roles are translated, within the platform administration, into access profiles to the different collections.

The graphical materialisation of a data flow also makes it easier to identify bottlenecks that may condition the long-term sustainability of the system. In its design, it is necessary to identify a series of elements that will determine the sequence and interaction between tasks. We summarise below those that seem to us to be the most critical in our case:

- CASE STUDY. *Mnemosine* creates collections within two possible scenarios:
 1. **Mass capture**. Import of information using Clavy's ETL capabilities.
 2. **Semi-automatic import**. This scenario starts from the need posed by a researcher who provides a repertoire of data, previously identified in a reliable source/repository. This is the use case represented in the flowchart below.

- OBJECTIVE. In this case the collections are created to serve the researcher by providing a working environment based on the idea of an intelligent library, capable of feeding a knowledge base (a digital library as well as a database for the development of knowledge, capable of creating interoperable semantic networks), reusable in future projects. To this end, it is critical to guarantee the quality of the data.

- RISKS. Once the process scenario has been delimited, it is necessary to identify threats to the achievement of the proposed objectives, which makes it possible to plan the necessary tasks, those responsible for them and the controls required to validate that the process does not encounter obstacles in its development. In the use case that serves as an example, problems in data quality (duplicate records, deficient authority control, broken links, erroneous data) or errors in the loading operation (for example, incorrect grammar in the import file) would penalise the functionality of the system, incorporating noise in searches or distorting the interrelation of data.
- RISK CONTROL. Once the possible points of failure have been detected, it is necessary to identify tasks that mitigate the probability of their occurrence or that offer a plan of action in such an eventuality. In the scenario described above, a content curation phase is essential to validate the structure and content of the data import file as a precautionary measure before loading it into the system.
- USER ROLES. When defining tasks, it is important to define the roles of the users who are going to interact with the solution and their corresponding access profiles. Having more capacity for action on the repository than is required for the tasks entrusted is a risk, in addition to those already identified. At the other extreme, defining profiles that are too restrictive reduces the agility of the workflow. Therefore, it is advisable to establish a middle ground, which provides the greatest possible transparency in the interaction with the system, without taking unnecessary risks.
- INPUT/OUTPUT. Input and output elements of the process. In this case, the input document is the upload file itself and the output is the datasets generated by the new collection, which must be published as a result of the project in open access repositories to contribute to the generation of new knowledge from the reuse of data.
- DETAIL OF SUB-PROCESSES AND TASKS. Once the use scenario, its objective, risks and actors have been delimited, we are in a position to break down the process with each of the activities to be carried out. In the use case we describe, four major sub-processes can be identified in the creation of a new collection:
 1. Data localisation: the operation of creating the load file with a field structure understandable by *Clavy*, i.e. in accordance with the

Mnemosine grammar. The responsibility for these tasks lies with the researcher himself, advised by the LOEP Group research team.

2. Content validation and curation. To avoid duplication, it is important to define a prior validation milestone that ratifies the need for a new collection specialising in the subject matter proposed by the researcher. Once it has been verified that the system with the current coverage cannot meet the need raised, the researcher proceeds to prepare the import file with the necessary fields and values. This content must be analysed and verified according to the controlled vocabularies and the *Mnemosine* authority control, in order to then model the cataloguing scheme that the data load will require. These tasks are undertaken by the LOEP team to ensure the consistency of the information in the repository.
3. Data import. This is carried out by *Clavy's* technical administration, which is undertaken by members of the ILSA Group. In this phase, a space for the new collection must be enabled before importing the data. It is very important in this sub-process to define the action to be taken in the event of an error in the upload, in order to proceed to the rollback of the operation, with the aim of reverting the situation in the database.
4. Analysis and export of results. After the creation of the new collection and its review and commissioning, it is necessary to close the process with the publication of the resulting datasets in the open access repositories used by *Mnemosine*: Zenodo and Github.

In addition, in this type of workflow it is also advisable to schedule periodic maintenance tasks that allow for a global review of the data model, in order to detect inconsistencies and optimise indexes for the efficient operation of the search engine. Interaction operations with the system should also be reviewed from time to time, in order to identify bottlenecks that condition the technical or operational scalability of the solution or the need to update and extend the coverage of data in existing collections.

Below is the flow chart representing the main tasks and actors described above:

Figure 6 Flow chart for semi-automatic creation of new collections in Mnemosine (source: own elaboration).

On the other hand, although it may be tedious, it is good practice to document in writing the workflows and periodic maintenance operations, at least in the case of

the most critical processes, as is the case in *Mnemosine* with the creation of new collections. Although it may seem unnecessary, the fact of graphically materialising a process known by all those involved is an invaluable aid in decision-making regarding the evolution of the system and its strategy. It is a common mistake in this type of solution to approach growth horizontally, with new content and themes, while neglecting vertical evolution, which ensures the permanent updating and expansion of existing collections and their associated functionality.

Finally, as already indicated, the definition of workflows should be incorporated into a process of continuous improvement, guided by an explicit roadmap or action plan, which allows us to identify as priorities those actions that bring us closer to the final objective. In a tool such as *Mnemosine*, the need to evolve its features as an intelligent library and innovation laboratory - in short, a digital platform for research - requires combining strategies of a scientific nature - new subjects and expansion of sources - with others of a technical nature: improvements in navigation, additional functionality, etc.

Challenges and constraints

The *Mnemosine* Digital Library was awarded by the International Association of Hispanic Digital Humanities as the Best tool, resource, infrastructure developed in 2021²¹. This award has meant an important support for the work of the Research Group *La Otra Edad de Plata* of the Complutense University of Madrid, directed by Dolores Romero López, in its eagerness "to rewrite with data the digital history and cultural memory of the Silver Age of Spanish Literature" through this collaborative platform.²²

However, this type of infrastructure requires the implementation of continuous improvement mechanisms to expand its functionality and content. The main problem faced by *Mnemosine*, like many other facilities in the academic field, is the lack of funding because it penalises its permanent updating and evolution. The management of this type of resources through closed research projects corresponds to working models in analogue environments, of a static nature, which are not appropriate for digital environments. On the other hand, although there are research groups permanently linked to the platform, dedication to this type of activity is not recognised as a merit, which forces them to be programmed as a parallel activity to other tasks of immediate performance, with the consequent cost of effort.

²¹ <https://humanidadesdigitaleshispanicas.es/resolucion-de-la-iv-edicion-premios-hdh/>

²² <https://www.unir.net/actualidad/vida-academica/unir-y-la-hdh-clausuran-el-congreso-cientifico-sobre-las-humanidades-digitales-con-la-entrega-de-reconocimientos/>

Apart from these issues, which transcend the platform's capacity for action, there are a series of actions that we believe should be addressed, as soon as possible, for their evolution at a technical level, beyond the creation of new collections or the expansion of data in existing ones. This is the case of the following initiatives:

- Optimise the architecture of main and auxiliary tables.
- Extend text annotation and geolocation functionalities to new collections.
- Improve search engines and navigation patterns to enhance the usability of the system.
- Explore new analysis cases, based on linked data, to extend the content coverage shown in the "Visualisations" section.
- Extend the security model to incorporate new roles to support content curation tasks, currently the least automated and therefore most costly process in the system.
- Enhancing the contribution of new content to *Wikidata*

In short, our intention is to consolidate and expand *Mnemosine's* capabilities as an open science laboratory, providing researchers with an intelligent platform that will effectively support their work in broadening and enriching new perspectives of analysis within our object of study: the evolution and impact of hitherto neglected cultural manifestations within the literary production of the Silver Age.

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